

METRO RAIL CONSTRUCTION AND ITS EFFECTS ON ROAD USERS

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Abstract:

Metro Rail is a mass rapid transportation system and also environment friendly. It is also a modern system of transportation. To overcome the future demand and also to make a short and less time consuming transportation system, the Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh has taken this project. It is a fast and time saving transportation system which is really needed for Dhaka. But during construction, similar to other countries the road users & inhabitants nearby have to face some problems. This study covers to find out the problems faced by the road users in the construction area. In this study it has found that, the vehicular traffic used this road has considerably decreased about 52 percent than before and after being a less number of vehicles, the average speed has also decreased at 1.1 km/h where the average speed in Dhaka city is 7 km/h. To compare the results, traffic data prepared by MRT (Mass Rapid Transit) authority before construction of metro rail has used. The results demonstrate that, the effects of construction of metro rail heavily imply the traffic and road users in the construction areas.

Keywords: Construction, Mass rapid transportation system, Metro rail, Motorized, Travel modes.

1. Introduction:

Dhaka City is the capital of the People's Republic of Bangladesh. Dhaka Metropolitan Area (DMA) is one of the world's largest city, with a population of 18.89 million [1]. It is also the 4th most densely populated city in the world [2]. The population density in Dhaka Metro is 46,997/km² or 121,720/sq. mi, [3]. Being the capital; Dhaka is one of the largest motorized cities in the world [4].

For this huge number of population, Dhaka city's traffic system is considered to be one of the most chaotic ones in the world [5]. Currently the City transportation in DMA heavily relies on road traffic, where the travel modes such as automobile, bus, and rickshaw are mixed. The minimum road requirement is 25% for a standard city, whereas Dhaka has only 7% road of its total area which is creating huge traffic [6]. Over the last few years the transportation problem of Dhaka City has visibly been deteriorating steadily. Citizens constantly complain about the unbearable twin problems of traffic jam and air pollution [5]. To reduce of those problems and to connect the industrial area such as Gazipur, Mirpur, Narayanganj etc to central part of Dhaka city, the Government of Bangladesh are working rapidly. In Recent years, The Government completed some mega projects such as Hatirjhil project, Mohakhali Overpass, Bijoy Shoroni-Tejgaon Link Road, Banani Overpass, Mirpur-Airport Road Flyover, Jatrabari Flyover, Moghbazar-Malibagh Flyover and some National Highway likes N1- Dhaka-Chittagong Highway, N2- Dhaka-Sylhet Highway, N3-Dhaka-Mymensingh Highway, N4-Joydebpur-Jamalpur Highway, N5- Dhaka-Banglabandha Highway etc.

Some projects are under construction. Currently, metro rail system is in under construction in Dhaka, the capital and largest city of Bangladesh. Together with a separate BRT (Bus Rapid Transit) system it has been long called for to solve the extreme amount of traffic jams and

congestion that occur throughout the entire city on a daily basis, among the heaviest in the world. It is a part of the 20-year long Strategic Transport Plan (STP) chalked out by the Government's Transport Coordination Authority (DTCA) [7].

Mirpur is one of the prominent regions of Dhaka city, established in 1962; it is located to the north-east of the city. It is bounded by Pallabi Thana to the north, Mohammadpur Thana to the south, Kafrul to the east, and Savar Upazila to the west. Total area of Mirpur is 58.66 km² (22.65 sq. mi). Around 1,074,232 people are living in this area (BBS report November 10, 2011). The population density is 16,838/km² (43,610/sq mi) of this area, (BBS report November 10, 2011). Mirpur is an important part of Dhaka city that's why this area has been selected for the research.

The deal for construction of the 20.1 kilometers (12.5 mi)[8] Line 6, costing \$2.8 billion, was signed by the Bangladesh with the Japan International Cooperation Agency on 20 February 2013.[9] This first route, originally projected to start from Uttara, a northern suburb of Dhaka, to Sayedabad, in the south of the capital,[10] was eventually extended north to Uttara and truncated south to Motijheel.[11]

Each train will hold up to 1800 passengers. With 56 trains to be in service by 2019, Dhaka Metro is projected to serve more than 60,000 passengers per hour by 2021, with wait times of approximately 4 minutes.[12] The entire route will be able to be travelled in less than 40 minutes at an average speed of 100 km/h (62 mph), expected to drastically reduce the number of private cars on Dhaka's streets as well as their potentially 7-hour-long standstills. The metro rail would be noise-free, with noise barriers and vibration-free lines, and the cars would be made of stainless steel and aluminum alloy".[13] The system plans to use magnetic contactless Integrated Circuit ticketing commonly also known as smart cards. Platform screening door (PSD) barriers used in the platform level will increase safety and increase efficiency. When the service is in full operation, trains of six air-conditioned spacious cars will arrive every four minutes going each way at each of the 16 stations[13].

2. Methodology:

At first the study area has selected. Currently MRT Line-6 is connecting the big and mostly populated Mirpur area, with other metro rail lines being added in the future. As MRT line-6 is in under construction through Mirpur which is a big part and also in the city area, so the route of MRT line-6 from Mirpur 12 to Agargaon has been selected as our study area. The traffic count has done in three points in Mirpur 12, Mirpur 10 and Agargaon in both directions during a week. The speed of the vehicle has calculated using GPS (Geographic Positioning System). To compare the results with previous data, the survey reports done by metro rail authority in 2014 (before metro rail construction) were collected as secondary data. At the same time for collecting primary data, field survey was conducted to identify the effects of surrounding peoples, footpath users and specially the effects of peoples while crossing the road at various points of the selected route. The primary and secondary data then analyzed and manipulated to achieve the objectives.

3. Results and Discussions:

The comparative results of traffic count during this research (i.e. during metro rail construction) and a result from the survey report prepared by metro rail construction authority before metro rail construction in 2014 have been shown in the table. This result is the average summary of one week traffic count. The vehicle has been categorized as Motorized Traffic (MT) (e.g. Jeep, car, motorcycle, auto rickshaw, micro bus, bus, truck), Non-Motorized Traffic (NMT) (e.g. rickshaw and van). The survey results were multiplied by PCU (Passenger Car Unit), where G. Total means the gross total. The traffic count has done in two ways at every point.

Table 1: Comparison of traffic count before and during the construction of metro rail.

Traffic Count at Various Points From Mirpur 12 to Agargaon Road								
Summary Sheet								
Location: Mirpur-12, Mirpur-10, Agargaon								
Survey Location	Direction	Total MT (PCU)		Total NMT (PCU)		G. Total (PCU)		Remarks
		Before	Present	Before	Present	Before	Present	
Mirpur 12	Mirpur 12 to Mirpur-10	991	498	683	737	1603	1236	22.90% Less than before
	Mirpur-10 to Mirpur 12	949	923	919	879	1868	1802	3.54% Less than before
Mirpur10	Mirpur 10 To Agargaon	1653	742	970	242	2622	983	62.50% Less than before
	Agargaon to Mirpur 10	1497	710	992	289	2489	1000	59.82% Less than before
Agargaon	Agargaon To Farmgate	1765	1223	1037	876	2802	2099	25.10% Less than before
	Farmgate To Agargaon	1558.67	1102	850.5	700	2409	1802	25.20% Less than before

In the above table it is found that the average daily traffic has decreased at about 33.18% than before the construction of metro rail. From Mirpur to Agargaon a major part of carriageway has blocked for metro rail construction. Although the width of the road has decreased, the traffic volume demand did not decrease. As a result this less amount of daily traffic creates a huge traffic jam which kills lots of working hours of the road users.

Figure 1: Gross total two way traffic count during and before the construction of metro rail from (a) Mirpur 12 to Mirpur 10 (b) Mirpur 10 to Mirpur 12 (c) Mirpur 10 to Agargaon (d) Agargaon to Mirpur 10 (e) Agargaon to Farmgate (f) Farmgate to Agargaon.

Figure 2: Traffic speed in Mirpur and and average speed in Dhaka.

The average speed of the vehicle in Dhaka City is 7 KMPH (Dhaka Tribune, July 19, 2017) where the same in Mirpur is 1.1 KMPH and that in some of the place which is free from construction effects is 2.8 kmph which is considerably low.

3.1 Effects on pedestrian traffic and local peoples:

The effect on Pedestrian traffic and local people has listed below by field survey.

- For the construction work the due to store materials and for boundary wall in footpath it has become narrow, for this reason Pedestrian traffic and local people facing many problems in their regular movement.
- Peoples are facing various health hazards especially for dust and mud created due to water logging.
- Due to the blockage in the middle of road along longitudinal direction pedestrian, local people and also business traders are sufferings a lot while crossing road.
- Peoples, traders and nearby institutions faced great problems during the period of excavation work as water , gas supply and sometimes electricity are interrupted several times during that time.

Figure 3: Suffering of pedestrian for (a) mud (b) Construction wall covering the footpath and business institution and (c) water logging

4. Conclusions:

Due to Metro Rail Construction, road width has decreased and for this there is a huge congestion of traffic although about 33.18% less traffic use this road than before. Speed of the vehicle in the area has considerably decreased to 1.1 kmph whereas the average speed in Dhaka city is 7 kmph. However some of the private vehicle owners have changed their route instead using this road, which creates congestion in all around the Dhaka. For pedestrian it has become so difficult to use the road especially on road crossing. However future study may be conducted using these data and adding carriageway width and road capacity can give more authentic, reliable, definite and comprehensive findings.

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References:

- [1] Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS), Statistics and Information Division (SID), Ministry of Planning, p. 67-69.
- [2] Statistical Pocket Book, 2015, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics. December 2013. Archived from (PDF) on 24 April 2015. Retrieved 14 May 2015.
- [3] Population & Housing Census-2011" (PDF). Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics. p. 41
- [4] Khan, M. A. , (2007). When shall we get rid of Dhaka city traffic jam? Bitter Truth. The Daily Star, Bangladesh.
- [5] Khaled Mahmud, Khonika Gope & Syed Mustafizur Rahman Chowdhury, Possible Causes Causes & Solutions of Traffic Jam and their Impact on the Economy of Dhaka City.
- [6] The New Republic" Magazine-July 3, 2014.
- [7] About MRT Line-6". Dhaka Mass transit Company Ltd. Retrieved 28 January 2017.
- [8] Japan provides funds for Dhaka Metro rail system". *Railway-Technology.com*. Retrieved 24 October 2015
- [9] Bangladesh, Japan strike deal for \$2.8-bln Dhaka metro rail". *Global Post*. 20 February 2013. Archived from the original on 21 May 2013. Retrieved 21 May 2013.
- [10] Muhith to sit with armed forces to resolve metro rail site dispute". *The Financial Express*. 25 June 2011.
- [11] "In 37 minutes". 26 June 2016. Retrieved 25 July 2016
- [12] Bdnews24.com. "Dhaka metro rail to carry 60000 peoples per hour" Retrieved 23 September 2012
- [13] Sun, the Daily. "Metro rail construction in progress". Metro rail construction in progress-Daily-sun.com. Retrieved 28 January 2017.